

Pottan : BA.

Darzi etc.

MISC

Tunp Shahr : Dargwan

1 P1A

2 P1B

3 ~~P1C~~ P1D

4 P1E

5 P1E bag 2

6 P1F, P1H, P1K

7 P1G + P4

8 P1J

9 ~~P1I~~

10 P 2 and P 3 (P2 in Medical, P3 in kt Mill)

11 Rayin 2B + da 2S

12 Z 6A Darzi

13 Z 6A Darzi

14 Z 6E Darzi

15 Z 6A Darzi

16 Tunp - Kharg MC

17 Tunp - Kharg B

18 Jagin 1, 3, 4, Maruzin 3, 4
Q 3 Q 4

19 Maruzin A, B. Maruzin 2
Q 1 Q 2

18 1/2
2

1 Mezar Mardi P17

2 Mezar Mardi

3 Sush Kalat P19

4 Tunp - Kharg 1A P13

5 Tunp - Kharg 1A

6 Tunp - Kharg 1A B + Tunp - Musarabad + Tunp - Sush (3rd Mill) P18

7 Kharg P14 2

8 Q alah Kuchek -> P7

9 Namurdi 2 P16

10 P 5

11 P 6

12 P 6

13 Jagin 2 + Cheraghabad 3

14 Cheraghabad 2

15 Cheraghabad 4

~~scribble~~

15

P20 Q alah - Gang -

Kwar Sodal I P8

Kwar Sodal I

Kwar Sodal I

Kwar Sodal 2 - P9

Cheraghabad 1.

Cheraghabad 1

Namurabad 1.

7 1/2

Maruzin 1	1	Jagin
2		
3		
4		
Cheraghabad 1	5	
2	6	
3	7	
4	8	

Record of SHAHABAD - Islamic site (P3?)

Record of Kharg 1 + 2 (labelled as mch)

Record of NAMURDI 1. P 11 + P 12.